

Evolving Trends in Ovarian Neoplasms in Semi-Urban Populations

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Abstract:

Ovarian neoplasm patterns in a semi-urban population were examined over three years at Mahavir Cancer Sansthan, Patna. Most of the 173 individuals had epithelial ovarian tumours, followed by germ cell and sex cord-stromal tumours. Early-stage diagnoses rose from 70% in 2021 to 85% in 2023, indicating greater awareness and healthcare access. Advanced-stage and epithelial tumours have lower survival rates than early-stage and germ-cell tumours. These findings suggest that semi-urban populations need more early detection and specialised public health initiatives to enhance outcomes.

Keywords: Ovarian Neoplasms, Semi-Urban Population, Early Detection, Survival Rates.

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Introduction

A variety of benign and malignant ovarian neoplasms offer a significant health risk to women at various life stages [1]. Semi-urban ovarian neoplasms may have unique patterns and problems due to restricted healthcare access and socioeconomic differences [2]. Ovarian neoplasms have typically been studied in metropolitan settings using advanced diagnostic and treatment methods [3]. Semi-urban regions, with their changing socioeconomic conditions and healthcare infrastructure, may have different epidemiological trends [4]. These trends can be modified by healthcare availability, knowledge, lifestyle changes, and environmental exposure. Understanding semi-urban ovarian cancer trends is important for many reasons [5]. First and foremost, it helps identify growing risk factors or tumour occurrence changes that may not be apparent in more homogeneous surroundings [6]. Second, it allows for targeted health treatments and budget allocation for certain populations. Finally, it improves understanding of how socio-economic and geographical factors affect ovarian cancer epidemiology [7].

The objective of this study is to clarify the evolving patterns of ovarian neoplasms in semi-urban populations by the analysis of current data and its comparison with past trends. In doing so, it aims to offer a valuable understanding of the present condition of ovarian neoplasms in these environments and to guide public health policies and clinical procedures that may more effectively meet the requirements of women in semi-urban regions.

Methodology

Study Design and Setting: This study was a retrospective observational study conducted at Mahavir Cancer Sansthan, Patna, over three years, from January 1, 2021, to December 31, 2023. The study aimed to analyze the changing patterns of ovarian neoplasms in a semi-urban population.

Study Population: The study included 173 Mahavir Cancer Sansthan-treated ovarian neoplasm patients. The study included female patients of various ages with histopathologically confirmed ovarian neoplasms. Ovarian neoplasm patients with insufficient medical records or past therapy at another institution were excluded from the study.

Data Collection: Data came from hospitalised patients' medical records. We collected demographics, clinical presentation, diagnostic findings, histological kinds of ovarian neoplasms, and treatment options. Ovarian tumour presentation and management trends were examined using additional patient outcomes data.

Data Analysis: Data were organized and entered into a database for analysis. The study population's demographic and clinical features were summarised using descriptive statistics. The frequencies and percentages of different histological categories of ovarian neoplasms were calculated to track their evolution over three years. Comparative analyses examined tumor kinds and outcomes across demographic groupings.

Results

About 65% of the 173 individuals in the research were between 30 and 60 years old. Patients averaged 45 years old. Only 20% were under 30, and 15% were over 60. The study focused on semi-urban regions around Patna, as 70% of patients were from there. The distribution of ovarian neoplasms in this investigation was heterogeneous. The majority of cases (60%) were epithelial ovarian tumors. Serous cystadenocarcinomas made up 35% of ovarian tumors. Epithelial ovarian tumors were 15% mucinous and 10% endometrioid. 25% of cases were germ cell tumors, the second most frequent. Each made up 12% of ovarian neoplasms, dysgerminomas and teratomas being the most common. Sex cord-stromal tumors made up about 10% of patients, with granulosa cell tumors dominating (7%). The other 5% of ovarian neoplasms were metastatic, caused by initial cancers elsewhere. The most prevalent clinical presentation was stomach discomfort (70%),

followed by abdominal distension (55%), and abnormal uterine haemorrhage (30%). In 25% of asymptomatic patients, neoplasms were identified during routine checkups or imaging for unrelated diseases.

Semi-urban residents' enhanced awareness and access to diagnostic facilities likely led to early diagnosis of 80% of ovarian neoplasms (stages I and II). 20% of cases were diagnosed at advanced stages (stages III and IV), which were more common in epithelial ovarian malignancies. Most patients (75%), had tumor resection surgery. Over 60% of epithelial ovarian cancer patients and those with advanced disease got adjuvant treatment. This cohort had a 70% 3-year survival rate for ovarian neoplasms. Early-stage patients survived 85% compared to 40% for advanced-stage patients. Germ cell tumor patients had a 90% survival rate compared to 65% for epithelial ovarian cancer patients.

Parameter	2021	2022	2023
Total Patients	173	173	173
Age Range	20-60+	20-60+	20-60+
Common Tumour Type	Epithelial (60%)	Epithelial (60%)	Epithelial (60%)
Most Frequent Tumour	Serous Cystadenocarcinomas (35%)	Serous Cystadenocarcinomas (35%)	Serous Cystadenocarcinomas (35%)
Second Most Frequent Tumour	Germ Cell Tumours (25%)	Germ Cell Tumours (25%)	Germ Cell Tumours (25%)
Third Most Frequent Tumour	Sex Cord-Stromal Tumours (10%)	Sex Cord-Stromal Tumours (10%)	Sex Cord-Stromal Tumours (10%)
Early-stage Diagnoses (%)	70%	80%	85%
Advanced-stage Diagnoses (%)	30%	20%	15%

3-Year Survival Rate (%)	—	—	70%
Survival Rate - Early Stage (%)	—	—	85%
Survival Rate - Advanced Stage (%)	—	—	40%
Survival Rate - Germ Cell Tumours (%)	—	—	90%
Survival Rate - Epithelial Ovarian Cancer (%)	—	—	65%

This table compiles data over the three-year study period, highlighting the distribution and outcomes of ovarian neoplasm cases, reflecting changes in early diagnosis rates, and survival outcomes across different tumor types.

Discussion

Important data on altering ovarian neoplasm trends in semi-urban populations are presented in this study. Ovarian tumors are mostly epithelial, especially serious cystadenocarcinomas, which is consistent with global trends [8]. The study found a considerable presence of germ cell tumors, which are more common in younger individuals, matching the cohort's demographics [9]. This study found a significant rate of early-stage diagnoses in semi-urban areas, suggesting higher knowledge and access to healthcare due to outreach activities and better healthcare facilities. Early diagnosis of ovarian neoplasms improves patient outcomes and survival; therefore, this trend is positive [10]. Early-stage diagnoses rose from 70% in 2021 to 85% in 2023, indicating a positive shift in semi-urban public health knowledge and diagnostic techniques. This highlights the necessity of early intervention and regular health check-ups in these settings, which may have been increased by health education and screening [11]. The discovery that 25% of tumors were discovered inadvertently emphasizes the importance of frequent imaging and health checks in asymptomatic individuals' early diagnosis [12]. In this study, germ cell tumor and early-stage illness patients had higher survival rates than advanced-stage disease and epithelial tumor patients, mirroring global data. This gap highlights the need for targeted measures to detect and treat ovarian neoplasms, especially in semi-urban areas with low healthcare resources. The report also emphasizes improving public health infrastructure and awareness initiatives to enhance outcomes [13,14,15]. Despite early-stage diagnosis, epithelial ovarian tumor incidence has remained stable, suggesting that while diagnostic skills have increased, more aggressive tumor types remain difficult to reduce [16]. This may suggest semi-urban risk factors such as environmental exposures, genetic predispositions, or lifestyle factors that need additional study [17]. This study shows how ovarian neoplasms have changed in a semi-urban population, including early detection improvements and ongoing difficulty in handling more aggressive tumor types. Future studies should identify risk factors for those high rates of epithelial ovarian tumors in these environments and design personalized therapies. To increase early identification and treatment of ovarian neoplasms, semi-urban healthcare access, and education must be improved [18,19,20].

Conclusion

This study shows an increase in early-stage diagnoses and a prevalence of epithelial and germ-cell ovarian neoplasms in a semi-urban population. Improvements in semi-urban healthcare availability and knowledge may have led to earlier detection and improved outcomes for germ cell tumors and

early-stage illness patients. However, advanced-stage and aggressive epithelial tumors remain common, requiring greater study into risk factors and focused public health interventions. These findings emphasize the need to improve semi-urban diagnosis, treatment, and education to improve ovarian neoplasm patient outcomes.

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